

Zer0_ The amazing contribution of Indians

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Abstract

This pilot study of gathering the information on the amazing numerical digit Zero. Here in this paper evolution of tiny digit Zero and how the peoples were used in an ancient days. The contribution of great Mathematicians of various countries and how they used in the symbolized form of Zero with the evidence.

Introduction

Zero is a tiny and strange number and it is one of the greatest paradoxes of human thought. It means that both everything and nothing. It is a number and numerical digit used to represent numbers in numerals. It fulfills the prominent role in the many algebraic structures. Without zero, not only mathematics but all branches of sciences would have struggled for accurate and clearer definitions. As a digit, 0 is used as a placeholder in place value system. Without the invention of zero, the binary system and computer are not possible. It is a greatest invention on which every calculation depends. Even though zero is a tiny number but it can never be ignored and it holds the highest value today.

It is believed that, Babylon, the Mayans developed zero as a placeholder around A.D. 350 and used it to denote a placeholder in their elaborate calendar systems. Despite being highly skilled mathematicians, the Mayans never used zero in equations, however. Kaplan describes the Mayan invention of zero as the “most striking example of the zero being devised wholly from scratch.” concept wove its way down to India, but others give the Indians credit for developing zero independently.

1	┆	21	≪┆	41	≪≪┆
2	┆┆	22	≪┆┆	42	≪≪┆┆
3	┆┆┆	23	≪┆┆┆	43	≪≪┆┆┆
4	┆┆┆┆	24	≪┆┆┆┆	44	≪≪┆┆┆┆
5	┆┆┆┆┆	25	≪┆┆┆┆┆	45	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆
6	┆┆┆┆┆┆	26	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆	46	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆
7	┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	27	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	47	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆
8	┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	28	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	48	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆
9	┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	29	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	49	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆
10	≪	30	≪≪	50	≪≪≪
11	≪┆	31	≪≪┆	51	≪≪≪┆
12	≪┆┆	32	≪≪┆┆	52	≪≪≪┆┆
13	≪┆┆┆	33	≪≪┆┆┆	53	≪≪≪┆┆┆
14	≪┆┆┆┆	34	≪≪┆┆┆┆	54	≪≪≪┆┆┆┆
15	≪┆┆┆┆┆	35	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆	55	≪≪≪┆┆┆┆┆
16	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆	36	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆	56	≪≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆
17	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	37	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	57	≪≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆
18	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	38	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	58	≪≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆
19	≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	39	≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆	59	≪≪≪┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆┆
20	≪≪	40	≪≪≪		

0	1	2	3	4
	•	••	•••	••••
5	•	••	•••	••••
10	•	••	•••	••••
15	•	••	•••	••••
20	•	••	•••	••••
25	•	••	•••	••••
30	•	••	•••	••••
35	•	••	•••	••••
40	•	••	•••	••••
45	•	••	•••	••••
50	•	••	•••	••••
55	•	••	•••	••••
60	•	••	•••	••••
65	•	••	•••	••••
70	•	••	•••	••••
75	•	••	•••	••••
80	•	••	•••	••••
85	•	••	•••	••••
90	•	••	•••	••••
95	•	••	•••	••••
100	•	••	•••	••••

Figure 1: Ancient Babylon number system.

Figure 2: Ancient Mayans number system

The Sumerians' system passed through the Akkadian Empire to the Babylonians around 300 B.C. There, scholars agree, a symbol appeared that was clearly a placeholder — a way to tell 10 from 100 or to signify that in the number 2,025, there is no number in the hundreds column. Initially, the Babylonians left an empty space in their cuneiform number system, but when that became confusing, they added a symbol — double angled wedges — to represent the empty column. However, they never developed the idea of zero as a number.

The concept of zero first appeared in India around A.D. 458. Mathematical equations were spelled out or spoken in poetry or chants rather than symbols. Different words symbolized zero, or nothing, such as "void," "sky" or "space". The ancient Hindu symbol of circle with a dot in the middle known as bindu or bindhu, symbolizing the void and the negation of the self, was probably instrumental in the using of a circle as a representation of the concept of zero.

Figure 3: The ancient Hindu symbol of circle with a dot representation of the concept of zero.

The ancient Indian mathematician Aryabhata was aware of concept of Zero, as well as the use of large numbers up to 1018. In the place value system of Aryabhata's work, the zero concept was used, but he did not use a symbol for zero. The French mathematician Georges Ifrah argues that knowledge of zero was suggested in Aryabhata's place value system as a place holder for the powers of ten with null coefficients.

About Aryabhata

Aryabhata (475 A.D. – 550 A.D.) is the first well known Indian mathematician and astronomer. Born in Kerala, he completed his studies at the University of Nalanda at the age of 24 years. He wrote *Aryabhatiya* (499 A.D.) in the section Ganita (Calculations) of his astronomical treatise, he made the fundamental advance in finding the lengths of chords of circles, by using the half chord, rather than the full chord method used by Greek. He was the first to calculate the value of 'Pi' accurately to the fourth decimal point as 3.1416. (He gave it in the form that the approximate circumference of a circle of diameter 20000 is 62832). He also gave methods for extracting square roots, summing arithmetic series, solving indeterminate equations of the type $ax - by = c$, and also gave the table of Sines and gave the area of a triangle as "for a triangle, the result of a perpendicular with the half-side is the area". He also wrote a text book for astronomical calculations, *Aryabhatasiddhanta*. Even today, this data is used in preparing Hindu calendars (Panchangs). In recognition to his contributions to astronomy and mathematics, India's first satellite was named Aryabhata.

In 628, a Hindu astronomer and mathematician named Brahmagupta developed a symbol for zero — a dot underneath numbers. Brahmagupta's *BrahmaSphutaSiddhanta* is the first book that mentions Zero as a number. Hence Brahmagupta is considered the first to formulate the concept of zero. He gave rules of using Zero with negative and positive numbers.

Figure 4: Numbers used by ancient Hindus with Zero

About Brahmagupta

Brahmagupta(598 A.D. – 670 A.D) a Hindu astronomer and mathematician, is best known for work performed while head of the Ujjain astronomical observatory, one of the leading centers for astronomical and mathematical research in ancient India. At this time, outstanding mathematicians such as *Varahamihira* had worked there and built up a strong school of mathematical astronomy. He was developed a number of important mathematical concepts, investigated the motions of planets and other celestial bodies and arrived at a fairly accurate estimate of the length of the terrestrial year. His most contributions are mentioned in his *BrahmaSphutaSiddhanta* (The opening of the universe) in 628. The work was written in 25 chapters. The second work of mathematics and astronomy was the *Khandakhadyaka* written in 665 when he was 65 years old. He was likely born in northwestern India and spent the majority of his life in the city of Bhinmal, in the Indian state of Rajasthan.

He also developed mathematical operations using zero, wrote rules for reaching zero through addition and subtraction, and the results of using zero in equations. This was the first time in the world that zero was recognized as a number of its own, as both an idea and a symbol.

According to Brahmagupta in his *BrahmaSphutaSiddhanta* definition for zero is “***Subtracting a number from itself results Zero***” .

He gave some properties to prove zero as a number, as follows:

*When zero is added to a number or subtracted from a number,
the number remains unchanged.
A number multiplied by zero becomes zero.*

He also gave arithmetical rules with positive (**fortune**) and negative (**debt**) numbers.

*A debt minus zero is a debt.
 A fortune minus zero is a fortune.
 Zero minus zero is a zero.
 A debt subtracted from zero is a fortune.
 A fortune subtracted from zero is a debt.
 The product of zero multiplied by a debt or fortune is zero.
 The product of zero multiplied by zero is zero.
 The product or quotient of two fortunes is one fortune.
 The product or quotient of two debts is one fortune.
 The product or quotient of debt and a fortune is a debt.
 The product or quotient of fortune and a debt is a debt.*

Throughout the dark ages, western mathematics was held back by the Roman's traditional number system. The first to think differently was Leonardo Fibonacci. He was a merchant's son, born in the Italian city of state Pisa, late in the twelfth century. In Pisa he studied the work of Euclid and other Greek mathematicians, when he was still a boy. He move to the North Africa and got an education in Arabic culture as he traveled around the Mediterranean to Constantinople, Egypt and Syria. He recognized that the Hindu-Arabic numbers then with the help of Indian mathematicians who developed a concept of Zero as a number with various proofs along with place value system in India. Later **Fibonacci** was so impressed with the easy of Hindu-Arabic numerals along with Zero that he wrote a book entitled **Liber abaci**. In his work, he recognized that the Hindu-Arabic numerals, the numerals we use today.

Figure 5: shows how zero evolved in number system.

Conclusion

It is a greatest invention on which every calculation depends on Zero. Zero is a tiny number but it can never be ignored. So, the value of zero is well known today as it holds the highest value. So, hats off to those Indian mathematicians Aryabata and Brahmagupta.

“ZERO IS SUPPOSED TO BE NOTHING BUT WORKS WONDERS IF ON THE RIGHT SIDE.”

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